

Evaluation of Outcomes With Citalopram for Depression Using Measurement-Based Care in STAR*D: Implications for Clinical Practice

Article summary

This study, conducted by Trivedi et al. (2006), explores the effectiveness of citalopram, a selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor (SSRI), in treating major depressive disorder (MDD) in real-world clinical settings. It is part of the Sequenced Treatment Alternatives to Relieve Depression (STAR*D) initiative, focusing on measurement-based care to evaluate treatment outcomes and predictors of remission.

Objectives and Methods

The primary goals were to determine remission and response rates for MDD patients and to identify baseline factors influencing these outcomes. Conducted across 41 clinical sites, the study enrolled 2,876 outpatients aged 18–75 with nonpsychotic MDD. Participants received flexible doses of citalopram for up to 14 weeks, with symptom and side effect monitoring guiding dosage adjustments. Remission was the primary endpoint, defined by a Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HAM-D) score ≤ 7 or a Quick Inventory of Depressive Symptomatology-Self Report (QIDS-SR) score ≤ 5 .

Key Findings

- Efficacy:**
 - Remission rates were 28% (HAM-D) and 33% (QIDS-SR).
 - Response rate, defined as $\geq 50\%$ reduction in baseline symptoms, was 47% (QIDS-SR).
 - Outcomes were consistent across primary and psychiatric care settings.
- Treatment Characteristics:**
 - The mean exit dose of citalopram was 41.8 mg/day, with a treatment duration averaging 10 weeks.
 - Remission often occurred after 8 weeks of treatment.
- Predictors of Remission:**
 - Higher remission rates were associated with being female, Caucasian, employed, better educated, and having fewer psychiatric or medical comorbidities.
 - Poorer outcomes correlated with greater symptom severity, longer depressive episodes, and comorbid conditions like anxiety disorders.
- Safety and Tolerability:**
 - The medication was well-tolerated, with low discontinuation rates due to side effects among remitters (2%).

Implications

The study demonstrates that measurement-based care can enhance treatment outcomes in routine clinical settings. While remission rates align with controlled trials, the inclusion of comorbid conditions highlights the real-world complexity of treating MDD. The findings underscore the importance of adequate dosing and duration, as well as the potential to improve care through systematic symptom monitoring. In conclusion, the STAR*D approach shows promise for achieving better clinical outcomes, bridging gaps between research

findings and everyday practice. Further studies are recommended to validate these methods with other treatments.

Figure 1

The figure is a **CONSORT flowchart** illustrating the **participant flow in the STAR*D study** (Sequenced Treatment Alternatives to Relieve Depression). It details the process of screening, eligibility, and progression of participants in the study:

- **Screening:**
 - Total participants screened: **4,790**.
 - Exclusions: **613 participants** were either not offered consent or refused to consent.
- **Note:** Figure 1 shows the disposition of patients during the course of the study.

Figure 2

Shows the distribution of the exit scores on the **16-item Quick Inventory of Depressive Symptomatology, Self-Report (QIDS-SR)** for 2,876 outpatients with nonpsychotic major depressive disorder. The x-axis represents the QIDS-SR scores, ranging from 0 to 27, while the y-axis shows the percentage of participants.

- **Categories:**
 - Scores are grouped into five categories:
 - **No depression** (scores 0–5),
 - **Mild symptoms** (scores 6–10),
 - **Moderate symptoms** (scores 11–15),
 - **Severe symptoms** (scores 16–20),
 - **Very severe symptoms** (scores 21–27).
- **Key observations:**
 - The distribution is left-skewed, with most participants falling in the "no depression" to "mild symptoms" range.
 - The percentage peaks at scores around **4 and 5** (no depression/mild symptoms), then gradually declines as the scores increase.
- **Note:** A QIDS-SR score of **10** approximates a Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HAM-D) score of **13**.

Figure 3

The figure illustrates the percentage of 2,876 outpatients with nonpsychotic major depressive disorder achieving either remission or response based on the Quick Inventory of Depressive Symptomatology, Self-Report (QIDS-SR) scores, plotted by week of treatment. "Remission" (red bars, N=943) is defined as a QIDS-SR score ≤ 5 , while "response" (purple bars, N=1,343) is defined as an improvement of $\geq 50\%$ in QIDS-SR scores from baseline.

- Remission rates peak around the 6th week of treatment, with nearly 20% of patients achieving remission.
- Response rates increase steadily up to the 6th week, also peaking at approximately 20%, and then slightly decline in later weeks.

Note: Figure 3 shows the distribution of the time to first remission and response for those who ultimately achieved these outcomes, with remission occurring on average in 6.7 weeks (SD=3.8) and response in 5.7 weeks (SD=3.5).

Table 1

Table 1 summarizes the baseline features of the evaluable sample (N=2,876). The patients included in the evaluable sample did not differ from those excluded on any of the characteristics in Table 1 (data not shown). Approximately 62% of the participants were from psychiatric care settings. Minority representation was 24%. Depressive symptoms were moderate to severe (HAM-D >21). More than 75% of the patients met criteria for recurrent or chronic depression. The mean length of illness was 15.5 years. At study entry, subjects had an average of 3.3 general medical conditions.

Demographic Domain:

- **Race:**
 - Caucasian: 75.8%
 - African American: 17.6%
 - Hispanic: 6.6%
- **Gender:**
 - Male: 36.3%
 - Female: 63.7%
- **Age Groups:**
 - 18–30 years: 26.2%
 - 31–50 years: 48.0%
 - ≥51 years: 25.8%
- **Mean Age:** 40.8 years (SD=13.0).
- **Education (years):** Mean of 13.4 years (SD=3.2).

Social Domain:

- **Marital Status:**
 - Never Married: 28.7%
 - Married: 41.7%
 - Divorced: 26.5%
 - Widowed: 3.1%
- **Employment Status:**
 - Employed: 56.2%
 - Unemployed: 38.2%
 - Retired: 5.6%
- **Education Levels:**
 - < High school: 12.6%
 - High school but < college: 62.1%
 - ≥ College: 25.3%.
- **Income:** Mean monthly income = \$2,358 (SD= \$3,030).

Clinical Domain:

- **Age of Onset <18 years:** 37.8%.
- **Family History of Depression:** 55.6%.
- **History of Attempted Suicide:** 17.9%.
- **Recurrent Depression:** 75.7%.
- **Comorbid Axis I Psychiatric Disorders:**
 - Generalized anxiety disorder: 23.6%.
 - Social phobia: 31.3%.
 - PTSD: 20.6%.
 - Alcohol abuse/dependence: 12.0%.
 - Drug abuse/dependence: 7.4%.
- **Number of Comorbid Psychiatric Disorders:**
 - 0: 34.8%.
 - 1: 26.6%.
 - 2: 16.5%.
 - ≥4: 12.9%.
- **Length of Current Major Depressive Episode:** Mean = 24.6 months (SD=51.7).
- **Symptom Severity (e.g., QIDS-SR score):** Mean = 16.2 (SD=4.0).
- **Quality of Life Measures (e.g., 12-Item Health Survey):**
 - Physical Score: 48.7 (SD=12.1).
 - Mental Score: 25.6 (SD=8.2).

Table 2

The table provides information on treatment characteristics and end-of-study remission status for 2,876 outpatients with nonpsychotic major depressive disorder. Remission was defined as a Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HAM-D) exit score of ≤ 7 . The table compares patients who achieved remission (N=790) to those who did not (N=2,086).

Key Characteristics:

Maximum Dose of Citalopram (mg/day):

- **<20 mg:**
 - No Remission: 2.7%
 - Remission: 0.9%
 - Total: 2.2%
- **20–39 mg:**
 - No Remission: 22.4%
 - Remission: 28.9%
 - Total: 24.2%
- **40–49 mg:**
 - No Remission: 27.6%
 - Remission: 36.4%
 - Total: 30.0%
- **≥50 mg:**
 - No Remission: 47.3%
 - Remission: 33.8%
 - Total: 43.6%

Dose of Citalopram at Study Exit (mg/day):

- **<20 mg:**

- No Remission: 4.6%
- Remission: 1.2%
- Total: 3.7%
- **20–39 mg:**
 - No Remission: 26.5%
 - Remission: 29.4%
 - Total: 27.2%
- **40–49 mg:**
 - No Remission: 27.0%
 - Remission: 37.2%
 - Total: 30.7%
- **≥50 mg:**
 - No Remission: 41.9%
 - Remission: 32.1%
 - Total: 39.2%

Time in Treatment (Weeks):

- **<4 weeks:**
 - No Remission: 14.8%
 - Remission: 1.8%
 - Total: 11.2%
- **4–8 weeks:**
 - No Remission: 21.3%
 - Remission: 5.2%
 - Total: 16.9%
- **≥8 weeks:**
 - No Remission: 63.9%
 - Remission: 93.0%
 - Total: 71.9%

Mean and Standard Deviation (SD):

- **Number of Visits:**
 - No Remission: Mean = 4.5 (SD=1.6)
 - Remission: Mean = 5.5 (SD=1.1)
 - Total: Mean = 4.8 (SD=1.5)
- **Time to First Treatment Visit (Weeks):**
 - No Remission: Mean = 2.4 (SD=1.2)
 - Remission: Mean = 2.3 (SD=0.8)
 - Total: Mean = 2.3 (SD=1.1)
- **Time in Treatment (Weeks):**
 - No Remission: Mean = 9.3 (SD=4.4)
 - Remission: Mean = 12.6 (SD=3.6)
 - Total: Mean = 10.0 (SD=4.2)
- **Time from Final Dose to Study Exit (Weeks):**
 - No Remission: Mean = 4.4 (SD=3.7)
 - Remission: Mean = 6.6 (SD=3.7)
 - Total: Mean = 5.0 (SD=3.8)

Notes:

- Remission is associated with higher doses of citalopram and longer durations of treatment.

- Patients achieving remission had more study visits and remained in treatment longer compared to those who did not achieve remission.

Table 3

The table presents a detailed comparison of adverse events, side effects, and attrition among two groups of patients: those who achieved **remission** (defined as **not achieve remission** (with a HA)

Key Findings:

1. **Frequency of Side Effects:**
 - Higher remission rates were linked to lower side effect frequency.
 - Remission was more common in patients experiencing side effects 10%–25% of the time (34.6%) than those with side effects 90%–100% of the time (19.5%).
2. **Intensity of Side Effects:**
 - Mild side effects were more prevalent in the remission group (35.9%) compared to severe side effects (9.6%).
 - Non-remission patients experienced more severe side effects (18.2%).
3. **Burden of Side Effects:**
 - Minimal-to-mild impairment was associated with higher remission rates (51.1%).
 - Severe impairment was more common among non-remission patients (9.9% vs. 4.4%).
4. **Serious Adverse Events:**
 - Non-remission patients had more psychiatric hospitalizations (2.6% vs. 0.3%) and suicidal ideation.
 - Deaths and hospitalizations for general medical conditions were rare overall.
5. **Intolerance to Medication:**
 - Higher in non-remission patients (11.2%) compared to remission patients (1.6%).

Conclusion:

Patients achieving remission reported fewer, less intense, and less impairing side effects, fewer serious adverse events, and greater medication tolerance compared to those who did not achieve remission.

Table 4

This table provides a comprehensive analysis of the factors associated with achieving remission in patients with **nonpsychotic major depressive disorder (MDD)**, based on two different depression assessment scales: the **17-Item Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HAM-D)** and the **16-Item Quick Inventory of Depressive Symptomatology, Self-Report**

(QIDS-SR). Remission is defined as achieving a score of ≤ 7 on the **HAM-D** or ≤ 5 on the **QIDS-SR**.

Key Influencing Factors:

1. **Race:**
 - Caucasians had the highest remission rates.
 - African Americans had lower odds (HAM-D OR: 0.70; QIDS-SR OR: 0.65).
2. **Gender:**
 - Females had higher remission odds (HAM-D OR: 1.35; QIDS-SR OR: 1.16, both significant).
3. **Marital Status:**
 - Married patients had the highest remission rates; never married patients had significantly lower rates (HAM-D OR: 0.71).
4. **Employment & Education:**
 - Employment increased remission odds (HAM-D OR: 0.70).
 - Higher education ($\geq$ college) was associated with greater odds (HAM-D OR: 1.31).
5. **Insurance:**
 - Private insurance correlated with the highest remission rates, while public insurance was linked to lower odds (HAM-D OR: 0.61).
6. **Comorbid Psychiatric Conditions:**
 - Disorders like GAD, OCD, PTSD, and substance abuse significantly reduced remission rates.
 - Somatoform disorders showed the strongest negative impact (HAM-D OR: 0.41).

Less Influential or Non-significant Factors:

- Hispanic ethnicity, family history of depression, age, and treatment setting (primary vs. specialty care) showed no major impact on remission.

Additional Findings:

- **Multiple comorbidities** (≥ 3) significantly lowered remission odds.
- Higher income and lower symptom severity were strongly linked to better outcomes.

Conclusion:

Socio-demographic, clinical, and socio-economic factors, particularly education, employment, and psychiatric comorbidities, play significant roles in remission rates. Targeted interventions for at-risk groups may improve outcomes.

Table 5

Table 5 presents pretreatment features associated with remission after controlling for baseline symptom severity and other factors. Lower remission rates were linked to various

demographic, socioeconomic, and baseline functional measures. Consistent findings were observed across different assessment tools.

Authors:

Madhukar H. Trivedi,

Endowed Title

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School

Medical School

Department

Psychiatry | Public Health

Graduate Programs

Clinical Psychology

Biography

Madhukar Trivedi is Professor of Psychiatry, Chief of the Division of Mood Disorders, and Director of the Center for Depression Research and Clinical Care at UT Southwestern Medical Center. He earned his MBBS and MS in Baroda, India, completing his residencies in Psychiatry at University General Hospital, Baroda, India and Henry Ford Hospital, Detroit, Michigan. He completed his fellowship at UT Southwestern, where he now serves as Betty Jo Hay Distinguished Chair in Mental Health and Julie K. Hersh Chair for Depression Research and Clinical Care. Certified by the American Board of Psychiatry and Neurology, Dr. Trivedi is an established clinical and translational researcher with extensive experience serving as PI and Co-PI on several single and multi-site clinical trials funded by NIH, foundations and industry sponsors.

Dr. Trivedi's research over the last 25 years has focused on understanding the neurobiology and psychology of depression and bipolar disorder, with a particular focus on developing an empirical basis for improving treatment of depression. Dr. Trivedi and his team have been involved in many of the pivotal studies involving the establishment of efficacy of antidepressant treatments (medications, psychotherapy, exercise, complimentary treatments, devices, etc.), examining next steps in treatment resistant depression to develop algorithms and guidelines, and developing and validating biomarkers in order to reach the goal of precision medicine for mood disorders. Among his most notable studies are the Establishing Moderators and Biosignatures of Antidepressant Response for Clinical Care (EMBARC) trial, Combining Medications to Enhance Depression Outcomes (CO-MED) trial, Sequenced Treatment Alternatives to Relieve Depression (STAR*D) study, and the Texas Resilience Against Depression (T-RAD) study.

His numerous awards include the National Depressive and Manic-Depressive Association Scientific Advisory Board, the Psychiatric Excellence Award from the Texas Society of Psychiatric Physicians (TSPP), the Gerald Klerman Senior Investigator Award, the American Psychiatric Association (APA) Award for Research, and the American College of Psychiatrists (ACP) Award for Research in Mood Disorders. For six consecutive years, Dr. Trivedi has been named a Global Highly Cited Researcher by Clarivate Analytics. He is also a member of numerous other professional organizations, including the American College of Neuropsychopharmacology (ACNP), the American College of Psychiatrists (ACP), the American Medical Association (AMA), the American Psychiatric Association (APA), the Dallas County Medical Society, the Society of Biological Psychiatry (SBP), the Texas Medical Association (TMA), and the Texas Society of Psychiatric Physicians (TSPP). Dr. Trivedi currently serves as Deputy Editor of the *American Journal of Psychiatry* and as president of the American Society of Clinical Psychopharmacology (ASCP).

- **Medical School**

Baroda Medical College (1980)

- **Internship**

S.S. General Hospital (1981), Psychiatry

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M.D. A. John Rush,

Augustus John Rush (born December 15, 1942) is an internationally renowned psychiatrist. He is a professor emeritus in Duke-NUS Medical School at the National University of Singapore (NUS), and adjunct professor of psychiatry and behavioral sciences at Duke University School of Medicine. He has authored and edited more than 10 books, and over 600 scientific journal articles that are largely focused on the diagnosis and treatment of depressive and bipolar disorders.

Education and early life

Rush grew up in New Jersey with his younger sister. He graduated valedictorian from the Pingry School, an independent, college preparatory country day school in New Jersey. Rush earned his bachelor's degree in biochemistry, cum laude, from Princeton University in 1964, and his medical degree from the Columbia University College of Physicians & Surgeons in 1968. Following his general medical internship at Passavant Hospital,

Northwestern University, Chicago, Illinois, he served as a general medical officer in the U.S. Army in Nuremberg, Germany. Following an additional year of government service in the Special Action Office for Drug Abuse Prevention in Washington, D.C., [4] he completed his psychiatric residency at the Hospital of the University of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia, Pennsylvania. There, he established the Depression Clinic with Manoochehr Khatami, M.D. He collaborated with his mentor Aaron T. Beck M.D. in the specification and initial testing of cognitive therapy for depression.

Career and research

As assistant professor in the Department of Psychiatry and Behavioral Sciences, University of Oklahoma, he led the third year medical student rotation in psychiatry and founded the Depression Clinic. He then joined the Department of Psychiatry, University of Texas Southwestern Medical Center at Dallas as associate professor, Professor and subsequently Vice Chair in Psychiatry. He was later also appointed Vice Chair and Professor in the Department of Clinical Sciences at UT Southwestern Medical Center at Dallas. Subsequently, as Professor and Vice Dean of Clinical Sciences at Duke-NUS Medical School in Singapore from 2008 to 2013, he established and developed specialized programs to launch and support patient-oriented research careers for clinicians by creating the Academic Medicine Research Institute, and a program in clinical research for third-year medical students.

His research has focused on the development and testing of innovative treatments for depressive and bipolar disorders including medications, medication combinations, somatic treatments, psychotherapy, and disease management protocols. [3] Rush's work is widely recognized nationally and internationally, and has received awards from many professional organizations including the American College of Psychiatrists, American Psychopathological Association the National Alliance for Research in Schizophrenia and Affective Disorders, the American Psychiatric Association and the Society for Biological Psychiatry, among others. In 2014, Thomson Reuters recognized Dr. Rush as one of the “World’s Most Influential Scientific Minds”.

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Ph.D. Andrew A. Nierenberg,

Dr. Andrew Nierenberg has been at the Massachusetts General Hospital since 1992, where he holds his current positions. He is also Honorary Professor in the School of Medicine, Faculty of Health at Deakin University, Geelong Australia.

Dr. Nierenberg has published over 500 papers and has been listed in The Best Doctors in America for the treatment of mood and anxiety disorders in every edition since 1994. In 2000, he was awarded the Gerald L. Klerman Young Investigator Award and in 2014 the

Gerald L. Klerman Senior Investigator Award by the Depression Bipolar Support Alliance. In 2013, Dr. Nierenberg was awarded the prestigious Brain and Behavior Research Foundation Colvin Prize for outstanding achievement in mood disorders research. In 2014, he was awarded the Mentorship Award for Exceptional Mentorship in the Research Arena at MGH. In 2014, 2015, and 2016 he was listed among the World's Most Influential Scientific Minds by Thompson Reuters in recognition of ranking among the top 1% of researchers for most cited papers in psychiatry worldwide.

Dr. Nierenberg's primary interests are bipolar depression and novel treatments. He lectures extensively, teaches, supervises, and mentors junior faculty, has an active clinical practice, consults to industry, and conducts clinical trials funded by federal, foundation, industry, and philanthropic sources. He serves as a peer reviewer for over 35 psychiatric journals. Dr. Nierenberg is a member of the editorial boards of over 15 journals and is the editor of *Psychiatric Annals* and is a deputy editor of *Depression and Anxiety*.

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Dr. Louis Ritz is an emeritus faculty of the Department of Neuroscience within the University of Florida College of Medicine. He is co-author of the textbook *Medical Neuroscience*. He also is the director of a campus-wide Center for Spirituality and Health. The undergraduate honors students named Dr. Ritz the “2018 Honors Professor of the Year.”

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M.B.A. Grayson Norquist,

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Exemplary Psychiatrist Award and the American Psychiatric Association Distinguished Service Award. During his time in Mississippi he set up a large telehealth network to provide mental health and addictive services in underserved rural areas. While at NIMH he was involved in formulating national policy for improving mental health services across the United States. He has worked with international organizations, including the World Health Organization, to improve the delivery of mental health services in underserved areas around the world. As Chair of the Council on Quality Care at the American Psychiatric Association he has led the formulation of new quality and performance measures for mental health care. Specialties Psychiatry Geriatric Psychiatry Board Certifications ABMS Psychiatry/Neurology Fellowships UCLA School of Medicine Affiliations Emory Education & Training Medical School: University of Mississippi Internship: UCLA School of Medicine Residency: UCLA School of Medicine Honors & Awards NIH Director's Award NIH Special Service Award National Alliance on Mental Illness Exemplary Psychiatrist Award American Psychiatric Association Health Services Research Senior Scholar Award American Psychiatric Association Distinguished Service Award

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M.D. Barry Lebowitz,

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Barry Lebowitz Optometrist is Professor of Psychiatry and Deputy Director of the Sam and Rose Stein Institute for Research on Aging at the University of California, San Diego. He moved to UCSD in 2005 after a nearly 30-year career at the National Institute of Mental Health where he served as Chief of the Geriatrics Research Branch. A native of Boston, Massachusetts, Dr. Lebowitz is a graduate of McGill University and Cornell University. He was elected a Fellow of the Gerontological Society of America and an Honorary Fellow of the American Psychiatric Association and the American Association for Geriatric Psychiatry. The recipient of a number of awards, Dr. Lebowitz was most recently honored with the M. Powell Lawton Award of the Gerontological Society of America.

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Ph.D. Patrick J. McGrath,

Professor of Clinical Psychiatry Profile Headshot Overview Dr. McGrath is a specialist in the clinical psychopharmacology of mood and anxiety disorders. He is currently Co-Director of the Depression Evaluation Service at the New York State Psychiatric Institute which conducts research into all aspects of the diagnosis and treatment of mood disorders. Special current research interests of Dr. McGrath's include pharmacogenetics, which is the effort to determine genetic determinants of response to antidepressant medications; brain imaging using positron emission tomography (PET) and functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) to determine the biology of response to antidepressants; prediction of loss of response to antidepressant medication; and the effects of alcohol abuse and dependence on the response to antidepressants. Academic Appointments Professor of Clinical Psychiatry Gender Male Credentials & Experience Education & Training Columbia University College of Physicians and Surgeons Internship: New York-Presbyterian Hospital/Columbia University Medical Center Residency: New York-Presbyterian Hospital/Columbia University Medical Center Research Dr. McGrath's research has focused on the clinical psychopharmacologic treatment of mood disorders, including anxiety and co-morbid substance use disorders such as alcoholism. Major current projects include: A translational neuroscience study of combination of antidepressants to accelerate and enhance response; a preliminary trial of transdermal selegiline for bipolar depression. Research Interests Clinical Psychopharmacology of Mood Disorders Selected Publications McGrath PJ, Stewart JW, Quitkin FM, Chen Y, Alpert JE, Nierenberg AA, Fava M, Cheng J, Petkova E: A prospective study of predictors of relapse during fluoxetine treatment of major depression. *American Journal of Psychiatry* 2006; In Press McGrath PJ, Stewart JW, Petkova E, Quitkin FM, Amsterdam JD, Fawcett J, Reimherr FW, Rosenbaum JF, Beasley CM: Predictors of relapse during fluoxetine continuation or maintenance treatment of major depression. *Journal of Clinical Psychiatry* 2000;61: 518-524 McGrath PJ, Nunes EV, Stewart JW, Goldman D, Agosti V, Ocepek-Welikson K, Quitkin FM: Imipramine treatment of alcoholics with primary depression. *Archives of General Psychiatry* 1996;53: 232-240

M.D. Kathy Shores-Wilson,

Shores-Wilson K, Biggs MM, Miller AL, Carmody TJ, Chiles JA, Rush AJ, Crismon ML, Toprac MG, Witte BP, Webster JC. Itemized clinician ratings versus global ratings of symptom severity in patients with schizophrenia. *Int J Methods Psychiatr Res.* 2002;11(1):45-53. doi: 10.1002/mpr.122. PMID: 12459804; PMCID: PMC6878268.

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Ph.D. Melanie M. Biggs,

Title: Licensed Psychologist

Company: Melanie M. Biggs, PhD, LLC

Location: Dallas, Texas, United States

Melanie Biggs, licensed psychologist at Melanie M. Biggs, PhD, LLC, has been recognized by Marquis Who's Who Top Healthcare Professionals for dedication, achievements, and leadership in behavioral therapy.

With a wealth of experience spanning over three decades, Dr. Biggs has established herself as a prominent figure in the field of clinical psychology. Her academic journey includes a PhD from the University of Texas Southwestern Medical Center in 1993, complemented by a Master of Arts from Loyola College in Maryland, now Loyola University Maryland, in 1985 and a Bachelor of Science from Southern Methodist University in 1983.

Dr. Biggs's career trajectory has been marked by significant contributions, including her current role as a licensed clinical psychologist at the Center for Cognitive Behavioral Therapy, now Melanie M. Biggs, PhD, LLC, a position she has held since 2020. Prior to this, she served as an outpatient licensed psychologist at Live More Simply, Inc. from 2019 to the present and as a licensed clinical psychologist and behavioral health consultant for the Heart and Lung Transplant Teams at BSW Medical Psychology Consultants and BSW Heart & Lung Transplant Teams from 2017 to 2019. Her earlier career includes notable roles as a licensed clinical psychologist at the Dallas VA Medical Center from 2010 to 2017 and at UT Southwestern Medical Center from 1988 to 2010.

Dr. Biggs specializes in the treatment of adults with depression and anxiety and provides behavioral medicine consultations, further enriching her contributions to the field. Dr. Biggs's dedication and accomplishments have been recognized through various awards, including the Outstanding Achievement Award for Service Provided for the Sequenced Treatment Alternatives to Relieve Depression at UT Southwestern in 2003, and the Outstanding Contribution to The STAR*D Project or Trial for Mental Health Purposes in the same year.

Outside of her professional endeavors, Dr. Biggs remains actively engaged in civic activities, volunteering with a breast cancer group. She is an active member of several professional associations, including the Dallas Psychological Association, the Association for Behavior and Cognitive Therapies, and the American Psychological Association. She attributes her success to a strong work ethic and her internal drive, as well as the invaluable support of her husband and family.

Looking ahead, Dr. Biggs envisions expanding her center to provide supervision for therapists learning Cognitive Behavioral Therapy, with a focus on extending clinical and training services. She is passionate about sharing her experiences and insights with aspiring professionals, emphasizing the importance of learning, pacing oneself, and embracing the journey in the field of clinical psychology.

Ph.D. G.K. Balasubramani,

- Additional affiliations
- January 2001 - present
- University of Pittsburgh

- Department of EpidemiologyPittsburgh, United States
- Position
- Senior Statistician
- Description

Major Research Interest: Sample survey design and analysis, Missing data analysis, multiple imputation for survey non response, Permutation and Randomization tests in biomedical studies, applied data analysis in clinical trials.

Education

- June 1987 - February 1992

Statistics

- July 1986 - June 1987
 - University of Madras

Statistics

- July 1984 - June 1986
 - University of Madras

Ph.D. Maurizio Fava, M.D

Psychiatrist-In-Chief, Department of Psychiatry Director, Division of Clinical Research, Mass General Research Institute; Executive Director, Clinical Trials Network & Institute Associate Dean for Clinical & Translational Research, Slater Family Professor of Psychiatry, Harvard Medical School Dr. Fava obtained his MD from the University of Padova School of Medicine where he completed residency training in endocrinology. He completed residency training in psychiatry at Mass General. He founded and was Director of the hospital's Depression Clinical and Research Program (DCRP) from 1990 to 2014. In 2007, he founded and is now Executive Director of the Mass General Psychiatry Clinical Trials Network and Institute (CTNI), the first academic CRO specialized in planning and coordination of multi-center clinical trials in psychiatry. Under Dr. Fava's direction, the DCRP became one of the most highly regarded depression programs in the country, a model for academic programs that link, in a bi-directional fashion, clinical and research work. Dr. Fava has been successful in obtaining funding as principal or co-principal investigator from both the National Institutes of Health and other sources for a total of more than \$95,000,000. His prominence in the field is reflected in his role as the co-principal investigator of STAR*D, the largest research study ever conducted in the area of depression, and of the RAPID Network, the NIMH-funded series of studies of novel, rapidly-acting antidepressant therapies. Dr. Fava is a world leader in the field of depression. He has authored or co-authored more than 800 original articles published in medical journals with international circulation, edited eight books, and published more than 50 chapters and over 600 abstracts. Dr. Fava is Editor-in-Chief of Mass General's Mind, Mood & Memory newsletter. Click on the link for more information and a free trial issue. Read More Departments, Centers, & Programs: Psychiatry Clinical Interests: Depressive disorders Psychopharmacology.

Acute and longer-term outcomes in depressed outpatients requiring one or several treatment steps: a STAR*D report Diagnosis and definition of treatment-resistant depression Efficacy and Safety of AXS-05 (Dextromethorphan-Bupropion) in Patients With Major Depressive Disorder: A Phase 3 Randomized Clinical Trial (GEMINI) The STAR*D study: treating depression in the real world

Journal :

American Journal of Psychiatry

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- Official Journal of the American Psychiatric Association
- Editor-in-Chief: Ned H. Kalin, M.D.
- **Impact Factor: 15.1 | Total Citations: 38,166**
- 2023 Journal Citation Reports® (Clarivate Analytics, 2024)

The **American Journal of Psychiatry (AJP)** achieved an impressive Impact Factor score of 15.1 in 2023, as reported by the Journal Citation Reports® (Clarivate Analytics, 2024). This metric reflects the journal's influence within the scientific community by evaluating how frequently its articles were cited. Essentially, the score implies that, on average, each article published by AJP during 2021 and 2022 received over 15 citations in 2023. Such a high Impact Factor ranks AJP among the top-performing journals, not only in psychiatry but also across all 21,522 indexed journals in the fields of science, technology, engineering, and medicine, surpassing 98% of them.

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AJP is published **monthly** and each issue includes original research articles, reviews, and other content related to psychiatry. The target audience includes psychiatrists, researchers, and clinicians, as well as clinical psychologists, medical students, residents, and other mental health professionals such as therapists, social workers, and addiction specialists. Policymakers and health administrators interested in mental health policy also form part of its readership.

The journal features a variety of article types, including original research presenting empirical findings in areas such as biological psychiatry, psychopharmacology, neurobiology, genetics, epidemiology, and psychotherapy. Randomized controlled trials and translational research bridging basic science and clinical practice are also commonly published. It includes review articles that synthesize key topics in psychiatry, meta-analyses of clinical trials, and theoretical or conceptual papers that propose new models for understanding psychiatric disorders. Commentary pieces, editorials, letters to the editor, and perspectives on current

challenges in psychiatry are regularly included, along with case reports highlighting rare or instructive clinical scenarios.

The journal covers a broad range of topics, including mood disorders such as depression and bipolar disorder, schizophrenia and other psychotic disorders, anxiety disorders, personality disorders, addiction and substance use disorders, age-related psychiatric issues like dementia, and child and adolescent mental health concerns. Cutting-edge treatment methods, such as gene therapy and neuromodulation, are also discussed.

AJP has a high citation rate and is among the most referenced journals in psychiatry globally. It regularly publishes groundbreaking studies that shape clinical practice and influence health policy, making it an indispensable resource for professionals in mental health fields.